

NOTES

The dye is obtained by adding the diazotised solution to a cooled solution of the naphthol, it is purified through high boiling solvents like chlorobenzene and analysed for nitrogen. Colour, m.p. and other properties are given in Table 1.

Dyeing: It was carried out in the usual way for azoic dyeing—temp. of the bath 60°C and material—liquor ratio of 1 : 20. After thirty minutes the hank was squeezed and passed through neutral diazotised *p*-rosaniline solution. After boiling with 1% soap solution for half an hour, it is dried and tested for fastness to soaping, bleaching, rubbing and light. The action of soap solution (8 g/litre) at 90–100°C for thirty minutes was studied. The shade not affected at all was graded as 5 and that with poor resistance as 1. The conditions for rubbing and light fastness tests are the same as those described by us in the previous communications¹, the only difference being that light fastness was determined in a Fade-o-meter.

Acknowledgement

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Reference

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Phenolic Aldoximes as Indicators for the Direct NTA Titration of Iron

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THE substances reported in literature as indicators for the direct titration of ferric ions with nitrilo-triacetic acid (NTA) are chromeazurole-S¹, pyrocatechol violet², and N-benzoyl-N-phenyl-hydroxylamine³. The present article reports the use of salicylaldoxime and β -resoreylaldoxime as indicators for the direct NTA titration of ferric ions.

Both these substances give violet colour with ferric ions. The endpoint is a sharp colour change from violet to yellow on titration with NTA. The optimum pH range is 1.5–2.5. Addition of four drops of 1.0% indicator solution gives satisfactory results. The titration can be satisfactorily carried out in the temperature range 15–50°C. The end point can be detected even in 1 ml of 0.001M solution of ferric nitrate, thus microtitration with NTA is feasible with these indicators.

The titrations of synthetic solutions were carried out at pH 1.0. At 2.8 mg concentration of iron, 100 times excess of Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Cl⁻, Br⁻, ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, 50 times excess of Be²⁺ and UO₂²⁺, 25 times excess of Pd²⁺, 10 times excess of Ag⁺,

5 times excess of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Al³⁺, Ni²⁺, Mg²⁺, and twice the excess of Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cr³⁺, Co²⁺, could be tolerated. Cu²⁺, Th⁴⁺, Zn⁴⁺ and anions forming stable complex with iron such as phosphates, vanadates, molybdates and tungstates interfered at all levels.

Synthetic solutions containing more than one foreign ions were also analysed with the help of these indicators at pH 1.0. Results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC SOLUTIONS

Taken	Found Fe ³⁺ mg	
	Salicyl-aldoxime	β -Resoreylaldoxime
1. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +50 mg Na ⁺ + 5 mg Ag ⁺	2.80	2.82
2. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +10 mg Pd ²⁺ + 50 mg K ⁺	2.80	2.80
3. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +15 mg Ca ²⁺ + 25 mg NH ₄ ⁺	2.82	2.80
4. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ + 5 mg Sr ²⁺ + 5 mg Ba ²⁺	2.80	2.80
5. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +20 mg Fe ²⁺ + 5 mg Al ³⁺	2.80	2.77
6. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ + 1 mg Co ²⁺ + 1 mg Ni ²⁺	2.80	2.80

Suggested procedure: Take 5 ml aliquot of solution containing ferric ions, bring the pH to 1.5, add four drops of 1.0% solution of indicator and titrate against 0.01M solution of NTA to light yellow colour.

Applications: An indigenous iron ore having the following percentage composition was also analysed by the suggested procedure.

Fe₂O₃ 92.8, Al₂O₃ 1.54, SiO₂ 3.07, CaO 0.3
TiO₂ 0.1, MgO 0.28, P 0.10, S 0.03

1.84 g of the ore was weighed accurately, the ore was brought into solution by standard method and diluted to 250 ml. A 2 ml aliquot of this solution was diluted to 100 ml and two 2 ml aliquots of the solution were then analysed as per the suggested procedure. The titre values of 0.01M, 6.82 ml and 6.84 ml NTA correspond to 3.81 mg and 3.82 mg respectively which are in good agreement with the calculated values of 3.82 mg.

The suggested indicators are superior to pyrocatechol violet and N-benzoyl-N-phenyl-hydroxylamine in that titrations can be carried out in the pH range 1.0–1.5 and are more selective.

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References

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